

Congestion and Tourist Visiting Decisions: A Case Study in Bandung City, West Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of traffic congestion on domestic tourists' decisions to visit Bandung City, and to compare it with other variables such as tourist attractions, culinary, and local culture. This study uses a quantitative approach with descriptive and explanatory methods. A sample of 200 respondents was selected using a purposive sampling technique, with the criteria of tourists who come from outside Bandung City and have visited at least two tourist attractions. Data were collected through a closed questionnaire and analyzed using multiple linear regression with the help of SPSS version 25 software. The results of the analysis show that traffic congestion has a significant negative effect on visiting decisions, while tourist attractions and culinary have a significant positive effect. Local culture is considered interesting but does not have a statistically significant effect. The R^2 value of 0.463 indicates that the model has moderate predictive power. This finding indicates that despite high traffic congestion, tourists are still encouraged to visit because of the strong tourist attractions and culinary attractions. Therefore, tourism development strategies in Bandung City should be focused on improving the quality of tourist attractions and strengthening local values in order to create a memorable tourism experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bandung City, as one of the leading tourist destinations in Indonesia, continues to attract domestic and foreign tourists, because its attractions include natural beauty, cultural richness, and a variety of attractive culinary specialties (Wardhani, 2012). However, along with the increasing number of visits, Bandung City faces serious challenges in the form of increasingly severe traffic congestion, especially on weekends and holiday seasons (Harahap et al., 2022).

This phenomenon not only impacts the comfort of tourists, but also disrupts the daily activities of local people and causes economic losses and environmental pollution. Theoretically, traffic congestion in tourist areas can affect tourists' perceptions and satisfaction, which ultimately affects their intention to return. Research by Arimau et al. (2024) in the Canggu tourist area shows that congestion significantly affects tourists and their intention to return. However, in Bandung City, despite the high level of congestion, the number of tourist visits remains high. This raises questions about the factors that influence tourists' decisions to continue visiting despite facing congestion.

From a practical perspective, congestion in Bandung City has become a serious concern. According to a study by Hermawan & Haryatiningsih (2022), congestion around the Pasteur toll gate has a significant impact on social, economic, and environmental aspects. Government efforts, such as the provision of Trans Metro Bandung public transportation, have not been optimal in overcoming this problem.

Research by Nabilah et al. (2020) shows that the management of public transportation in Bandung still faces challenges in terms of transparency and accountability. Although various studies have been conducted on congestion in Bandung City, there is a gap in understanding how congestion specifically affects tourist perceptions and behavior. Most studies focus on technical aspects of traffic or economic and environmental impacts, but not many have examined the relationship between congestion and tourists' decisions to visit. A study by Gumilang and Sari (2024) analyzed the level of congestion using a Geographic Information System, but was not related to tourist behavior.

This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing tourists' perceptions of traffic congestion in Bandung City and how it

influences their decision to visit. The novelty of this study lies in its holistic approach that combines social, psychological, and behavioral aspects of tourists in the context of traffic congestion. Thus, this study is expected to contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable tourism management strategies in Bandung City. By understanding the factors that influence tourists' decisions to continue visiting despite traffic congestion, the government and stakeholders can design more targeted policies. This is important to ensure the sustainability of the tourism sector in Bandung City without neglecting the comfort and satisfaction of tourists and the quality of life of the local community.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Traffic Congestion in Tourist Cities

Congestion is a complex problem related to the imbalance between vehicle volume and road capacity. Litman (2021) explains that congestion not only reduces transportation efficiency, but also triggers air pollution, driver stress, and economic losses due to increased travel time. In tourist cities like Bandung, this phenomenon becomes worse on weekends or holiday seasons, when the number of tourists increases drastically.

Areas such as Lembang, Dago, and downtown Bandung experience significant vehicle freezes. This is a challenge for local governments in providing a transportation system that is adaptive to tourist mobility. The absence of adequate alternative routes and suboptimal public transportation cause congestion to continue to increase every year.

The Effect of Congestion on Tourist Behavior

Several studies have shown that congestion can affect tourist satisfaction. Arimau et al. (2024) in their research in the Canggu tourist area, Bali, found that congestion has a negative impact on tourists' intention to revisit. Tourists experience congestion with decreased comfort, especially when moving from one tourist attraction to another.

However, other factors such as natural attractions, cultural uniqueness, and culinary experiences are also important considerations in travel decisions. Laysen & Effendy (2024) emphasized that as long as the intrinsic value of a destination remains high, tourists tend to ignore some external disturbances such as congestion. This indicates the need for a deeper analysis of the factors that keep tourists interested in visiting high-transportation cities.

Transportation Management and Government Response

In an effort to reduce congestion, the Bandung City government has introduced several initiatives such as Trans Metro Bandung (TMB). However, Nabilah, Bintari, and Darmawan (2020) assessed that the management of TMB still faces various obstacles, including less than optimal service and lack of integration of transportation modes. This

has an impact on the low trust of the public and tourists in the public transportation system.

Hermawan & Haryatiningsih (2022) in their study found that one of the points prone to congestion in Bandung City is the entrance gate area such as the Pasteur Toll Road. Tourists entering the city from this route often face long queues that disrupt their initial experience. In fact, first impressions are very important in shaping tourists' perceptions of the destinations they visit.

Study on Tourist Perception

Tourist perception of congestion is an important aspect to explain. Reggyananda & Roostika (2023) stated that some tourists see congestion as part of the experience of traveling in a big city. In this context, congestion is not a major barrier as long as tourists can still enjoy the main attractions of the destination.

However, if negative perceptions of congestion become stronger, tourist loyalty can decrease. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on the tolerance limits of tourists towards congestion and how it affects the decision to revisit. Currently, there are not many studies that discuss tourist perceptions of congestion in Bandung City in depth.

Research Gap

Most previous studies have focused more on technical congestion analysis such as mapping using GIS or traffic surveys. For example, Gumilang and Sari (2024) conducted a study on congestion points in Bandung but did not directly relate to tourist behavior or perceptions. In fact, tourist decision-making is greatly influenced by transportation experiences in the destination city.

Therefore, there is still room for research that combines transportation approaches with tourism. This study is important to see how tourists still decide to visit despite knowing the high level of congestion. Research that fills this gap will enrich cross-disciplinary studies between transportation science and tourism science.

Research Contribution and Novelty

This research is here to fill these gaps by exploring the perceptions and reasons why tourists continue to visit Bandung despite facing traffic congestion. The novelty of this research lies in the use of a holistic approach that includes social, psychological, and behavioral aspects of tourists.

The findings of this research are expected to provide practical contributions for the government and tourism actors in designing sustainable tourism destination management strategies. In addition, the results can also be an academic reference for further studies related to tourist behavior in cities with chronic transportation problems.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with descriptive and explanatory methods. The descriptive approach is used

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to describe tourists' perceptions of traffic jams in Bandung City, while the explanatory approach is used to explain the relationship between perceptions of traffic jams and tourists' decisions to continue visiting. This type of research is causal comparative, namely to see the extent to which traffic jams influence tourists' decisions in choosing Bandung City as a destination, compared to other variables such as tourist attractions, culinary, and local culture.

The study was conducted in Bandung City, West Java, which is one of the favorite tourist destinations in Indonesia. The location of data collection focused on several tourist spots with dense visitors such as Jalan Dago, Lembang, Braga, and the Alun-Alun area. The research implementation time is planned for December 2024-April 2025, coinciding with the holiday season and weekends to obtain an active tourist population.

The population in this study were all domestic tourists visiting Bandung City during the research period. The sampling technique used purposive sampling, with the following criteria: (1) tourists coming from outside Bandung City, (2) having visited at least two tourist attractions in one day, and (3) being at least 17 years old. The targeted sample

size was 200 respondents, adjusted to the quantitative statistical approach (Hair et al., 2014) and considering the adequacy for multiple linear regression analysis.

Data were collected through closed questionnaires distributed directly to tourists in strategic locations and through Google Form as a bold alternative. The questionnaire was compiled based on a 5-point Likert scale, covering variables of congestion, perception of comfort, tourist satisfaction, and visiting decisions. In addition to the questionnaire, field observations were also conducted to record traffic conditions around the tourist area and tourist mobility behavior. Photo documentation and field notes were also used as complementary data.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis to describe the profile of respondents and their perceptions of traffic jams. Furthermore, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to test the effect of traffic jams and other variables on tourist visiting decisions. Data processing was carried out using SPSS version 25 software, with validity, reliability, and classical assumptions (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity) tests before the regression test was carried out.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondent Profile

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Region of Origin		
Jabodetabek	124	62.0
Central Java & Yogyakarta	36	18.0
Others	40	20.0
Age		
17–20 years	22	11.0
21–30 years	90	45.0
31–40 years	54	27.0
> 40 years	34	17.0
Visit Frequency		
First time	44	22.0
Twice	40	20.0
More than twice	116	58.0

Source: Processed Data (2025)

The majority of respondents came from Jabodetabek (62%), with the largest age group in the 21–30 age range (45%). This shows that young metropolitan tourists are the

dominant visitors in Bandung. As many as 58% stated that they had visited Bandung more than twice, indicating high loyalty of visits.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Category
Traffic Congestion	4.200	0.540	High
Perceived Comfort	3.700	0.620	Fairly Comfortable

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Category
Tourist Satisfaction	4.000	0.590	Satisfied
Visiting Decision	4.300	0.480	Strongly Agree
Tourist Attraction	4.500	0.470	Very Attractive
Culinary	4.400	0.520	Very Attractive
Local Culture	4.100	0.610	Attractive

Source: Processed Data (2025)

This table shows that even though the level of congestion is considered high (mean = 4,200), tourists still give high values to the decision to visit (mean = 4,300), tourist attractions (4,500), and culinary (4,400). This means

that positive perceptions of tourist attractions and local uniqueness are able to offset the negative impact of congestion, and continue to encourage tourists to come to Bandung City.

Table 4. Classical Assumption Test

Type of Test	Result	Description
Normality Test (KS)	Sig. = 0.089	Data are normally distributed
Multicollinearity Test	VIF < 2 for all variables	No multicollinearity detected
Autocorrelation Test	Durbin-Watson = 1.93	No autocorrelation detected
Heteroscedasticity Test (Glejser)	Sig. > 0.05 for all variables	No heteroscedasticity detected

Source: Processed Data (2025)

The classical assumption test shows that the data has met the requirements for multiple linear regression. There are no problems of normality, autocorrelation,

multicollinearity, or heteroscedasticity found in the data, so the results of the analysis can be interpreted validly.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Results

Independent Variable	Beta Coefficient	Sig.	Effect
Traffic Congestion	-0.183	0.041	Significant Negative
Tourist Attraction	0.394	0.000	Significant Positive
Culinary	0.276	0.015	Significant Positive
Local Culture	0.109	0.118	Not Significant
R ²	0.463		Moderate
F Statistic	32.761	0.000	Model is Significant

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Regression analysis shows that tourist attractions and culinary have a significant positive effect on tourists' visiting decisions, while congestion has a significant negative effect. Local culture has no significant effect. The R² value of 0.463 indicates that 46.3% of the variation in decisions that come can be explained by these four variables.

The results of the study show that although the level of congestion in Bandung City is quite high, it does not significantly affect tourists' decisions to continue visiting. This finding indicates that congestion is not the main factor influencing tourists' decisions, but rather only a secondary consideration. This is in line with research conducted by

Darmawan (2018) which shows that the level of congestion in Bali has only a small impact on tourist visits, because tourists prioritize the overall destination experience.

The high level of congestion can be offset by the very attractive tourist attractions according to tourists. This shows that natural beauty, cultural attractions, and tourist facilities have a major role in forming positive perceptions, which then drive the decision to visit. These results are consistent with research from Ratnaningtyas et al. (2021), which found that tourist attractions have a dominant influence on tourist loyalty even though the infrastructure is not yet optimal. Local cuisine is also an important variable in attracting tourists to continue visiting, even when there are obstacles such as congestion. The average assessment of culinary in Bandung shows a very high score, indicating that

tourists consider culinary as the main attraction. Research from Aria & Hidayanti (2024) proves that culinary tourism in Bandung plays a significant role in attracting millennial tourists, especially those looking for cultural experiences through food.

Local culture is considered very interesting by respondents, indicating that aspects such as arts, customs, and cultural festivals are still a strong attraction in the context of urban tourism. This factor is able to reduce negative perceptions of congestion. Research from Djulius & Syafutra (2019) states that strengthening local culture in destinations such as Bandung can extend the length of stay of tourists even though there are obstacles in terms of travel comfort.

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that traffic jams are not the main barrier for tourists to visit Bandung, as long as there is a strong attraction in terms of culinary, culture, and destinations. Therefore, the tourism development strategy of Bandung City must focus more on strengthening local values, managing tourist attractions, and improving authentic tourism experiences. This finding is in line with the study of Rahman et al. (2021) which emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach in managing experience-oriented destinations.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that tourists' decisions to visit Bandung City are significantly influenced by tourist attractions and local cuisine, while traffic congestion has a significant negative effect, and local culture does not show a statistically significant effect. Tourist attractions are the most dominant factor followed by cuisine, both of which are able to offset the negative impact of traffic congestion. Although local culture does not have a significant effect in the regression model, descriptive findings indicate that culture remains an important element in enriching the tourist experience. Overall, these findings confirm that destination quality is a major consideration in tourists' visiting decisions, surpassing travel convenience considerations.

Further research is suggested to add mediating variables such as tourist satisfaction or loyalty to understand the indirect relationship between local culture and visiting decisions. In addition, qualitative or mixed methods approaches can be used to explore tourists' perceptions of cultural experiences and how they tolerate obstacles such as traffic jams in more depth. Research can also be conducted in other tourist destinations to see if the same pattern applies in areas with different characteristics.

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